

Effect of VAM inoculation on growth and yield of lowland rice.

Treatment ^a	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers (no./plant)	Mycorrhizal infection at harvest (%)	Grain yield (g/pot ^b)	Straw (g/pot ^b)
No NPK, no M	88	9	16.1	66.9	55.90
No NPK, with M	103	9	49.3	87.6	72.93
				(31)	(30)
With NK, no M	103.5	10	13.6	83.5	68.25
With NK, with M	104.5	12	50.0	103.5	79.75
				(24)	(17)
With NPK, no M	103	10	12.8	85.2	63.00
With NPK, with M	104	11	43.0	106.2	75.50
				(25)	(20)
LSD (P = 0.05)	ns	ns	23.6	18.1	15.3

^a M = inoculated with *G. fasciculatum*. ^b Figures in parentheses are percent increase over control.

in a separate experiment. Inoculation with *G. fasciculatum* raised mycorrhizal colonization (see table), but its effect on plant height and productive tillers was not significant. Grain and straw yield

increased significantly with VAM inoculation. Facilitating VAM infection by nursery inoculation, following the dry nursery method, can be used to achieve VAM benefits in lowland rice. ■

Effect of planting method and optimum seeding rate on biomass production and nitrogen fixation in *Sesbania rostrata*

A. Tirol-Padre and J. K. Ladha, Soil Microbiology Division, IRRI

We experimented with *S. rostrata* at IRRI Nov 1987-Jan 1988 to determine 1) optimum sampling size for measuring plant density, biomass, and acetylene-reducing activity (ARA), and 2) optimum seeding rate and planting method for higher biomass and N₂ fixation.

Seeding rates were 20, 40, and 60 kg/ha and planting methods were broadcast, row seeding with 15 cm between rows, and row seeding with 30 cm between rows. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with 3 replications. Plot size was 2 × 6 m. Biomass and ARA were measured 41 d after seeding (DAS).

For estimating plant density, the 30- × 30-cm sampling unit gave better precision than 30- × 60-cm or 60- × 60-cm for the same sampling area in all treatments. Efficiency appears higher with small samples taken many times rather than big samples taken a few times. Small sampling units are especially recommended for plots with uneven plant distribution. With the 30- × 30-cm sampling unit, the coefficients of vari-

ation (CV) of the mean (\bar{x}) for 4, 8, and 12 samples/block were 12.4, 8.8, and 7.2%, respectively.

For determining plant biomass, the two-plant sampling unit generally gave better precision than the four-plant unit when seed was broadcast or planted in rows. CV (\bar{x}) for 2, 4, and 6 samples/block were 14.6, 10.3, and 8.4%, respectively.

For ARA measurements, the 4-plant sampling unit generally gave better precision when seed was planted in rows (15-30 cm apart) and plant samples were taken from adjacent rows. CV (\bar{x}) for 2, 4, and 6 samples/block were 13.6, 9.6, and 7.9%, respectively. When plants were sampled from the same row or when seeds were broadcast, however, the two-plant sampling unit gave higher precision.

Effect of seeding rate and planting method on a) plant density of *S. rostrata*, b) biomass per unit area of *S. rostrata*. IRRI, 1988.

Row seeding generally resulted in higher germination rate than broadcast seeding, with more plants/m² and biomass/m² at 20 and 40 kg seed/ha. However, row seeding with 30 cm between rows had germination similar to broadcast seeding at 60 kg seed/ha.

When seed was broadcast or sown in rows with 15-cm spacing, increasing the seeding rate from 20 to 60 kg/ha increased the number of plants and plant biomass/m². But with 30 cm between rows, higher seeding rate increased the two parameters only up to 40 kg/ha (see figure); overcrowding within rows resulted in lower germination. Increasing the number of rows (i.e., decreasing the distance between rows to 15 cm) minimized crowding of seeds within rows. This explains why, at 60 kg seed/ha, plant density and biomass/m² were higher with 15 cm than with 30 cm between rows.

Planting method significantly affected ARA/plant, but seeding rate had no effect. Averages of ARA at three seeding rates were 12.1, 10.3, and 97 μmol C₂H₄/plant per h for broadcast, 15-cm row seeding, and 30-cm row seeding, respectively, with a standard error of the mean of 0.6. This seems to be related to the lower plant density, when seed was broadcast.

Planting method and seeding rate produced significant effects on ARA per unit area and on biomass per unit area. Estimated ARA per m² was 597, 823, and 746 μmol C₂H₄/plant per h for broadcasting, 15-cm seeding, and 30-cm seeding treatments, respectively, with a standard error of 50. ■